

THE PLACE AND DEVELOPMENT OF THE INTERTEXT PHENOMENON IN WORLD LITERATURE

Khasanov Sukhrob Shavkatovich

English language teacher of

Samarkand State Institute of foreign languages

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8069604>

Annotation. The phenomenon of intertext plays an important role in the development of world literature. Because, precisely because of this phenomenon, the images that have already existed in the world literature and are passing from language to language have not lost their place in fiction. This serves to increase the content of the works. We can find many types of intertext in world literature, especially in Western fiction. We can see this phenomenon given in epigraph, title, allusion, quotation, antonomasia, parody and other forms.

Key words. epigraph, title, allusion, quotation, antonomasia, parody

Here, one of the most commonly used types of intertext is quoting an epigraph, and almost all writers use various quotations that correspond to the content of their works as an epigraph. An example of this can be seen by Ernest Hemingway, one of the famous English writers, when he took Gertrude Stein's famous quote "You are all a lost generation" as an epigraph to his work "The Sun Also Rises" at the beginning of the century. This epigraph is so skillfully chosen by the writer that for the reader it seems as if it embodies the content of the entire work. We can also see another English writer, Mary Shelley, using a quote from „Paradise Lost” as an epigraph in the introduction to her „Frankenstein”:

One of the most common intertext symbols is the title, which is often used extensively in the literature of the English and Uzbek languages. For example, the English writer Richard Dawkins refers to the age of John Keats' "Lamia" by using the name "Unwoven Rainbow" in his work. Similarly, it is known that Edward FitzGerald's title "AS Wilderness" was taken from translations of "Umar Khayyam's Rubaiyat". Another famous writer, Brian Keenan, when he named his work "Wicked Cradle", was referring to the Holy Koran, which was translated by Arthur John Arbury at the same time.

Another great presenter of the phenomenon of intertextuality is the phenomenon of Antonomasia. We need to understand that the process of antonomasia is the process of replacing the name of a certain person in fiction with various expressions that describe him as "little corporal" instead of being called Napoleon.

Below are examples of English antonomasia:

Bard of Avon - William Shakespeare

Wise man - Suleiman

Philosopher - Aristotle

Iron Duke - Duke of Wellington

King of Pop - Michael Jackson

Intelligent man - Einstein

His Majesty - the king or a judge in court

Madman of Macedonia - Alexander the Great
Three musketeers - Athos, Porthos and Aramis

In the video series based on Harry Potter written by J. Rowling, we can see the phenomenon of antonomasia in the description of Voldemort, one of the characters in the work. In this case, without mentioning the name of the dangerous person, people call him "Who do you know" or "His name should not be mentioned". In this place, the writer emphasizes how dangerous that person is by using antonomasia, the main reason for this is that most wizards and witches are extremely afraid to say their names out loud.

We will see that it is possible to enter the intertext phenomenon in world literature through parody through certain works. In this case, "Parody" is a work created to imitate or comment on the original work in a satirical and sarcastic way of its theme, author, style or other purpose. As confirmation of this idea, we consider the following:

English examples:

A great example of intertextuality in world literature can be seen through parody in poetry: Kenneth Koch's poem "William Carlos Williams Variations on a Theme" is a parody of Williams's ultra-minimalist style, which is further ``by choosing together for a strange subject. The following is a parody of the poem "That's Just Saying" by William Carlos Williams: I have eaten **the plums**

that were in the icebox
and which you were probably
saving for breakfast
Forgive me they were delicious
so sweet and so cold

Mana, Kennet Kochning parodiyasi:
I chopped down **the house** that you had been
saving to live in next summer.

By changing the line "eat your prunes" to "crush your house", the metaphor seems to express an opinion about the value and melodrama of William's poem. Like poetic parody, novel parody is the main element of showing intertextuality: Graham Smith publishes "Pride and Prejudice and Zombies" in 2009. In this parody, Smith is a contemporary parody of Jane Austen's Pride and Prejudice, in which Graham portrays the popular trope of lovers and the popular zombie horror genre. . Graham's parody is a great success, as we can see that Graham-Smith imitated Austen's writing style in every detail. This parody of the creator is written with the spirit of great artistic artistry. In general, the work relies on the power of originality to show the dissonance between style and content, which makes this novel of his humorous and thoroughly entertaining.

In world literature, especially in Western and Eastern literature, we can see a wonderful form of intertextuality through myths: We should know that myth is the world in which humanity lives, the place of people in it, the creation of everything, the imagination of gods and heroes. is a story that is delivered to the reader.

Conclusion. In particular, we can see that the most wonderful examples of English mythology appeared during the long historical period of England. According to the creation, these works were developed by people in sequence and they were rejected in other times or replaced by other legendary stories, so a collection of legends is formed. At this point, we should emphasize that if we look at English literature, it cannot be denied that Greek mythology

occupies an important place in the works created by English writers, poets and dramatists. As an example, we can say that Athena, Minerva, Achilles, Apollo, Arcaida and several other mythological characters are often found in English literature. We can also say that "Greek Myths" serves as a precedent text not only in English literature, but also in the world literature scene. Because they are well known to ordinary people and readers. Because of this, we can easily understand them without any context.

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